

PROJECT REPORT ON GREEN HOUSE WITH SUSTANABLE ENERGY SYSTEM

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Project Report on

Green House with Sustainable Energy System

Controller

Summing

Fuel cell.

House

Temperature

Time offset: 0

Power

Time offset: 0

Introduction

Fuel cells are electrochemical devices that convert a fuel's chemical energy directly to electrical energy with high efficiency. With no internal moving parts, fuel cells operate similar to batteries. An important difference is that batteries store energy, while fuel cells can produce electricity continuously as long as fuel and air are supplied. Fuel cells electrochemically combine a fuel (typically hydrogen) and an oxidant without burning, thereby dispensing with the inefficiencies and pollution of traditional energy conversion systems.

Fuel cells forego the traditional fuel-to-electricity production route common in modern power production, which consists of heat extraction from fuel, conversion of heat to mechanical energy and, finally, transformation of mechanical energy into electrical energy. In a sense, our bodies operate like fuel cells because we oxidize hydrocarbon compounds in our food and release chemical energy without combustion.

Fuel cells function on the principal of electrolytic charge exchange between a positively charged anode plate and a negatively charged cathode plate. When hydrogen is used as the basic fuel, "reverse hydrolysis" occurs, yielding only water and heat as byproducts while converting chemical energy into electricity, as shown in Figure 1. Pollutant emissions are practically zero.

Figure 1. Conceptual Operation of a Fuel Cell.

Fuel Cell Types

Fuel cell types are generally characterized by electrolyte material. The electrolyte is the substance between the positive and negative terminals, serving as the bridge for the ion exchange that generates electrical current.

While there are dozens of types of fuel cells, there are six principle kinds in various stages of commercial availability, or undergoing research, development and demonstration. These six fuel cell types are significantly different from each other in many respects; however, the key distinguishing feature is the electrolyte material.

They are:

1. Alkaline Fuel Cell (AFC)
2. Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell (MCFC)
3. Phosphoric Acid Fuel Cell (PAFC)
4. Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC)
5. Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC)
6. Direct Methanol Fuel Cell

FC REACTANTS AND PRODUCTS

The Five Principal Types of Fuel Cells and their Electrochemical Reactions.

The following sections describe each of these fuel cell types.

Courtesy of UTC Fuel Cells

1) Alkaline

Alkaline Fuel Cells (AFCs) were the first type of fuel cell to be widely used for manned space applications. AFCs contain a potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution as the electrolyte. AFCs operate at temperatures between 100°C and 250°C (211°F and 482°F). Higher temperature AFCs use a concentrated (85wt%) KOH solution while lower temperature AFCs use a more dilute

KOH solution (35-50wt%). The electrolyte is contained in and/or supported by a matrix (usually asbestos) which wicks the electrolyte over the entire surface of the electrodes. A wide range of electro-catalysts can be used in the electrodes (e.g., Ni, Ag, spinels, metal oxides, and noble metals). The fuel supplied to an AFC must be pure hydrogen. Carbon monoxide (CO) poisons an AFC and carbon dioxide (CO₂) reacts with the electrolyte to form potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃). Even the small amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere (about 370 ppm) must be accounted for operation of an AFC (Hirschenhofer et al., 1998).

2) Molten Carbonate

Full-scale demonstration plants are now testing molten carbonate fuel cells (MCFCs). The electrolyte in an MCFC is an alkali carbonate (sodium, potassium, or lithium salts, i.e., Na_2CO_3 , K_2CO_2 , or Li_2CO_3) or a combination of alkali carbonates that is retained in a ceramic matrix of lithium aluminum oxide ($LiAlO_2$). An MCFC operates at 600 to 700°C where the alkali carbonates form a highly conductive molten salt with carbonate ions (CO_3^{2-}) providing ionic conduction through the electrolyte matrix. Relatively inexpensive nickel (Ni) and nickel oxide (NiO) are adequate to promote reaction on the anode and cathode respectively at the high operating temperatures of an MCFC (Baker, 1997).

MCFCs offer greater fuel flexibility and higher fuel-to-electricity efficiencies than lower temperature fuel cells, approaching 60 percent. The higher operating temperatures of MCFCs make them candidates for combined-cycle applications, in which the exhaust heat is used to generate additional electricity. When the waste heat is used for co-generation, total thermal efficiencies can approach 85 percent.

3) Phosphoric Acid

Phosphoric Acid Fuel Cell (PAFC) technology is the most mature of the types in use today. PAFCs use a concentrated 100% phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4) electrolyte retained on a silicon carbide matrix and operate at temperatures between 150 and 220°C. Concentrated H_3PO_4 is a relatively stable acid, which allows operation at

these temperatures. At lower temperatures, problems with CO poisoning of the anode electro-catalyst (usually platinum) and poor ionic conduction in the electrolyte become problems (Hirschenhofer et al., 1998). The electrodes typically consist of Teflon™-bonded platinum and carbon (PTFE-bonded Pt/C).

PAFC fuel cells produced by UTC Fuel Cells (previously named ONSI and International Fuel Cells) were the world's first commercially available fuel cell product (King and Ishikawa, 1996). Turnkey 200-kilowatt plants are now available and have been installed at more than 200 sites in the United States, Europe, and Asia (principally Japan). Operating at about 200°C, the PAFC plant also produces heat for domestic hot water and space heating, and its electrical efficiency is 36-40 percent. The development and implementation of this commercial fuel cell product is a result of several years of research development and demonstration by the U.S. Department of Energy, U.S. Department of Defense, Gas Research Institute.

4) Proton Exchange Membrane

Courtesy of Plug Power

The proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) is also known as the solid polymer or polymer electrolyte fuel cell. A PEMFC contains an electrolyte that is a layer of solid polymer (usually a sulfonic acid polymer, whose commercial name is Nafion™) that allows protons to be transmitted from one face to the other (Gottesfeld and Zawadinski, 1998). PEMFCs require hydrogen and oxygen as inputs, though the oxidant may also be ambient air, and these gases must be humidified. PEMFCs operate at a temperature much lower than other fuel cells, because of the limitations imposed by the thermal properties of the membrane

itself (Appleby and Yeager, 1986). The operating temperatures are around 90°C. The PEMFC can be contaminated by CO, reducing the performance and damaging catalytic materials within the cell. A PEMFC requires cooling and management of the exhaust water to function properly (Gottesfeld and Zawadinski, 1998).

5) Solid Oxide

Tubular SOFC. Courtesy of Siemens Westinghouse Power Corporation

Planar SOFC - Courtesy of Siemens Westinghouse Power Corp.

Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (SOFCs) are currently being demonstrated in sizes from 1kW up to 250-kW plants, with plans to reach the multi-MW range. SOFCs utilize a non-porous metal oxide (usually yttria-stabilized zirconia, Y2O3-stabilized ZrO2) electrolyte material. SOFCs operate between 650 and 1000°C, where ionic conduction is accomplished by oxygen ions (O⁼). Typically the anode of an SOFC is cobalt or nickel zirconia (Co-ZrO₂ or Ni-ZrO₂) and the cathode is strontium-doped lanthanum manganite (Sr-doped LaMnO₃) (Singhal, 1997; Minh, 1993).

SOFCs offer the stability and reliability of all-solid-state ceramic construction. High-temperature operation, up to 1,000°C, allows more flexibility in the choice of fuels and can produce very good performance in combined-cycle applications.

SOFCs approach 60 percent electrical efficiency in the simple cycle system, and 85 percent total thermal efficiency in co-generation applications (Singhal, 1997).

The flat plate and monolithic designs are at a much earlier stage of development typified by sub-scale, single cell and short stack development (kW scale). At this juncture, tubular SOFC designs are closer to commercialization.

6) Direct Methanol

Courtesy of Smart Fuel Cells

The direct-methanol fuel cell (DMFC) is similar to the PEM cell in that it uses a polymer membrane as an electrolyte. However, a catalyst on the DMFC anode draws hydrogen from liquid methanol, eliminating the need for a fuel reformer. While potentially a very attractive solution to the issues of hydrogen storage and transportation (particularly for portable applications), the principal problem facing the commercial application of the DMFC today stems from its relatively low performance in comparison to hydrogen fueled PEMFCs.

Fuel Cell-Benefits

- Environmental
- High Efficiencies
- Combined Cooling, Heat & Power (CCHP)
- Reliability
- Power Quality
- Permitting Ease
- Modularity
- "Distributed Generation-ness"

Environmental Acceptability

The environmental benefits of fuel cells are some of the main motivating forces in their development. These benefits include the zero- or near-zero-emission of criteria pollutants (NO_x, SO_x, CO, and hydrocarbons) and very low noise emissions.

Environmentally friendly fuel cell properties could eliminate consumer contempt for power generation close to their houses and businesses. While most consumers probably would prefer to have conventional electricity generated at a location far from their homes due to the noise and pollution, the benign nature of fuel cells makes them non-offensive even if placed in residential communities.

Fuel Cell System Efficiencies

High Efficiencies

Depending upon fuel cell type and design, fuel-to-electricity efficiency ranges from 30 to 60 percent (LHV). For hybrid fuel cell/gas turbine systems, electrical conversion efficiencies are expected to achieve over 70 percent (LHV). When byproduct heat is utilized, the total energy efficiency of fuel cell systems approaches 85 percent.

As shown in Figure 3, stand-alone fuel cell systems have the capability of reaching efficiencies greater than 50 percent, even at relatively small sizes (e.g., 10 kW). Hence, fuel cell systems could reduce the impact of electricity production on global climate change by reducing the amount of greenhouse gases emitted into the atmosphere per kilowatt-hour of power. They would also reduce resource depletion and dependence on fossil fuels by allowing more power to be harnessed from an same amount of fuel.

Combined Heat and Power (CHP) or Combined Cooling, Heat and Power (CCHP) Capability

High-quality heat is available for co-generation, heating, and cooling. Fuel cell exhaust heat is suitable for use in residential, commercial, and industrial co-generation applications.

The figure to the right compares conventional generation to CHP. On the left we see that the purchase of power from the grid must be supplemented with an onsite boiler to provide the same heating needs as what a fuel cell's waste stream (heat) could provide at no extra cost or investment.

The heat from a fuel cell can be used for a variety of purposes:

- Boilers: Two thermal loads for a boiler plant are make-up water and return water. If a boiler distribution system is maintained properly, make-up water requirements will likely be low. For high make-up water requirements, pre-heating boiler make-up water represents a good application for a fuel cell power plant. Load characteristics will depend on the loads on its thermal loop, time of year, and site specific factors.
- Domestic Hot Water (DHW) is used for a variety of purposes including showers, laundry, kitchen loads, etc. In dormitories or hotels, thermal loads typically peak in the morning and evening periods with little or no demand in the middle of the day and night.

- Space Heating Loops. Hot water space heating loops generally operate at temperatures that require the high-grade heat exchanger Thermal utilization is to the months where space heating is required.
- Swimming pools have both make-up water requirements (due to evaporation and spillage) and pool reheat requirements. The thermal load demand will vary depending on whether the pool is indoors or outdoors, the ambient temperature and humidity, the wind velocity, whether the pool is covered or not, the pool size and other site specific variables.
- Absorption Cooling Thermal Loads: Using a high-grade heat exchanger option, the fuel cell power plant can provide heat to an absorption chiller to provide cooling to a building. Absorption chillers create a thermal load for a fuel cell when no other loads are available. If electric rates are high in the cooling season, then displaced cooling using an absorption chiller can be cost-effective. Sites with longer cooling seasons or requiring continuous cooling (hospitals, etc.) are the best candidate sites for this technology

Reliability

Fuel cells are assumed to be superior to the grid because they are on site and subject to fewer disruptions (e.g. storms knocking down wires). With no moving parts, fuel cells will have less instances of failure than mechanical systems.

Today, the long-term performance and reliability of many of the fuel cell systems has not been significantly demonstrated to the market. Research, development and demonstration of fuel cell systems that will enhance the endurance and reliability of fuel cells are currently underway. The specific RD&D issues in this category include: (1) endurance and longevity, (2) thermal cycling capability, (3) durability in installed environment (seismic, transportation effects, etc.), and (4) grid connection performance.

Power Quality

Fuel cell electrical output can be configured to be computer grade. For example, systems have been configured to provide 99.9999+ percent uptime. Furthermore, fuel cell power plants can be set up in a range of electrical outputs. Individual fuel cell systems also can be arranged in series to meet increasing load demands.

Permitting Ease

Permitting and licensing schedules are short due to the ease of siting. Furthermore, fuel cell power installations are exempt from air emission permitting requirements in many U.S. states and provide flexibility under many federal, state and local air pollution standards.

Modularity

The fuel cell is inherently modular. It operates at near constant efficiency, independent of size and load. The fuel cell power plant can be configured in a wide range of electrical outputs, ranging from single kilowatt sizes up to multi-megawatt systems.

Distributed Generation

Distributed Generation (DG) refers to generation at or near the site of use (for example, at a near a building requiring power). Fuel cells are a form of DG, and can contribute to the establishment of a DG market because of their characteristics as described above. Instead of an electricity distribution infrastructure based on centralized power plants routing power through wires over long distances, fuel cells and DG make it attractive to spread small power plants throughout an electrical grid or a geographic area.

Such a configuration could:

- Reduce pollution
- Increase local and system reliability

- Increased power quality due to a potential freedom from troublesome frequency variations, voltage transients, dips, and surges. A fuel cell can be an attractive alternative to expensive uninterruptible power supplies, power-line filters, or energy storage systems used to condition grid electricity.
- Increase efficiency by reducing the distance electricity would have to travel from source to consumer.
- Reduce system maintenance cost (no transmission and distribution wires)
- Increased flexibility in system design, expansion and growth
- Reduction in customers' outage costs and experiences
- Increased response to changing loads
- Cogeneration benefits (heat capture)
- Reduction in time to respond to customers needs - fuel cell construction is quicker than central station units and large transmission improvements, making it easier to match incremental capacity additions to load growth. This reduces opportunity cost and risk relative to investing in large central station units.
- Customers are spending money installing power quality devices to alleviate power fluctuations, or bargaining for damage payments from generators. Fuel cell installations may mitigate or eliminate these situations.

Applications

There are many uses for fuel cells — right now, all of the major automakers are working to commercialize a fuel cell car. Fuel cells are powering buses, boats, trains, planes, scooters, forklifts, even bicycles. There are fuel cell-powered vending machines, vacuum cleaners and highway road signs. Miniature fuel cells for cellular phones, laptop computers and portable electronics are on their way to market. Hospitals, credit card centers, police stations, and banks are all using fuel cells to provide power to their facilities. Wastewater treatment plants and landfills are using fuel cells to convert the methane gas they produce into electricity. Telecommunications companies are installing fuel cells at cell phone, radio and 911 towers. The possibilities are endless.

For monthly updates on the latest fuel cell developments in all applications, sign-up (use the box to the far right of this page) to receive Fuel Cells 2000's monthly technology updates via email.

Stationary

More than 2500 fuel cell systems have been installed all over the world — in hospitals, nursing homes, hotels, office buildings, schools, utility power plants - either connected to the electric grid to provide supplemental power and backup assurance for critical areas, or installed as a grid-independent generator for on-site service in areas that are inaccessible by power lines.

Fuel cell power generation systems in operation today achieve **40 percent** fuel-to-electricity efficiency utilizing hydrocarbon fuels. Since fuel cells operate silently, they reduce noise pollution as well as air pollution and when the fuel cell is sited near the point of use, its waste heat can be captured for beneficial purposes (cogeneration). In large-scale building systems, these fuel cell cogeneration systems can reduce facility energy service costs by 20% to 40% over conventional energy service and increase efficiency to **85 percent**.

Telecommunications - With the use of computers, the Internet, and communication networks steadily increasing, there comes a need for more reliable power than is available on the current electrical grid, and fuel cells have proven to be up to 99.999% (five nines) reliable. Fuel cells can replace batteries to provide

power for 1kW to 5kW telecom sites without noise or emissions, and are durable, providing power in sites that are either hard to access or are subject to inclement weather. Such systems would be used to provide primary or backup power for telecom switch nodes, cell towers, and other electronic systems that would benefit from on-site, direct DC power supply.

Landfills/Wastewater Treatment Plants/Breweries - Fuel cells currently operate at landfills and wastewater treatment plants across the country, proving themselves as a valid technology for reducing emissions and generating power from the methane gas they produce. They are also installed at several breweries - Sierra Nevada, Kirin, Asahi and Sapporo. Untreated brewery effluent can undergo anaerobic digestion, which breaks down organic compounds to generate methane, a hydrogen rich fuel.

Transportation

Cars - All the major automotive manufacturers have a fuel cell vehicle either in development or in testing right now, and several have begun leasing and testing in larger quantities. Commercialization is a little further down the line (some automakers say 2012, others later), but every demonstration helps bring that date closer.

Buses - Over the last four years, more than 50 fuel cell buses have been demonstrated in North and South America, Europe, Asia and Australia. Fuel cells are highly efficient, so even if the hydrogen is produced from fossil fuels, fuel cell buses can reduce transit agencies' CO2 emissions. And emissions are truly zero if the hydrogen is produced from renewable electricity, which greatly improves local air quality. Because the fuel cell system is so much quieter than a diesel engine, fuel cell buses significantly reduce noise pollution as well.

Scoters - In spite of their small size, many scooters are pollution powerhouses. Gas-powered scooters, especially those

with two-stroke engines, produce tailpipe emissions at a rate disproportionate to their small size. These two-stroke scooters produce almost as much particulate matter and significantly more hydrocarbons and carbon monoxide as a heavy diesel truck. Fuel cell scooters running on hydrogen will eliminate emissions - in India and Asia where many of the population use them - this is a great application for fuel cells.

Forklifts/Materials Handling - Besides reducing emissions, fuel cell forklifts have potential to effectively lower total logistics cost since they require minimal refilling and significantly less maintenance than electric forklifts, whose batteries must be periodically charged, refilled with water, and replaced. Due to the frequent starting and stopping during use, electric forklifts also experience numerous interruptions in current input and output - fuel cells ensure constant power delivery and performance, eliminating the reduction in voltage output that occurs as batteries discharge.

Auxiliary Power Units (APUs) - Today's heavy-duty trucks are equipped with a large number of electrical appliances—from heaters and air conditioners to computers, televisions, stereos, even refrigerators and microwaves. To power these devices while the truck is parked, drivers often must idle the engine. The Department of Energy (DOE) has estimated the annual fuel and maintenance costs of idling a heavy-duty truck at over \$1,800 and that using fuel cell APUs in Class 8 trucks would save 670 million gallons of diesel fuel per year and 4.64 million tons of CO₂ per year.

Trains - Fuel cells are being developed for mining locomotives since they produce no emissions. An international consortium is developing the world's largest fuel cell vehicle, a 109 metric-ton, 1 MW locomotive for military and commercial railway applications.

Planes - Fuel cells are an attractive option for aviation since they produce zero or low emissions and make barely any noise. The military is especially interested in this application because of the low noise, low thermal signature and ability to

attain high altitude. Companies like Boeing are heavily involved in developing a fuel cell plane.

Boats - For each liter of fuel consumed, the average outboard motor produces 140 times the hydrocarbons produced by the average modern car. Fuel cell engines have higher energy efficiencies than combustion engines, and therefore offer better range and significantly reduced emissions. Iceland has committed to converting its vast fishing fleet to use fuel cells to provide auxiliary power by 2015 and, eventually, to provide primary power in its boats.

Portable Power

Fuel cells can provide power where no electric grid is available, plus they are quiet, so using one instead of a loud, polluting generator at a campsite would not only save emissions, but it won't disturb nature, or your camping neighbors. Portable fuel cells are also being used in emergency backup power situations and military applications. They are much lighter than batteries and last a lot longer, especially important to soldiers carrying heavy equipment in the field.

Micro Power

Consumer Electronics- Fuel cells will change the telecommuting world, powering cellular phones, laptops and palm pilots hours longer than batteries. Companies have already demonstrated fuel cells that can power cell phones for 30 days without recharging and laptops for 20 hours. Other applications for micro fuel cells include pagers, video recorders, portable power tools, and low power remote devices such as hearing aids, smoke detectors, burglar alarms, hotel locks and meter readers. These miniature fuel cells generally run on methanol, an inexpensive wood alcohol also used in windshield wiper fluid.

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